

A Proposed Genetic Algorithm Model to Improve Effort Estimation in Agile Software Development

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Abstract— One of the main difficult tasks in software development projects is an effort estimation accuracy. the project's estimated cost, duration, and maintenance effort early in the development life cycle is a big challenge to be achieved for software projects. Agile software projects require an innovative effort estimation model to help a constructive cost accurate estimation. The main focus of this paper is using the prediction model of genetic algorithm to improve the effort estimation accuracy by chromosomes that are made up of a gene pool that includes user stories, friction factors, implementation Level factor, and dynamic forces.

Index Terms—Genetic Algorithm, Agile Software Development, Effort estimation.

1. Introduction

The management of the software development project is the process of planning, organizing, staffing, monitoring, controlling, and software project leading. the life cycle of the project consists of four phases Project initiation, project planning, project execution, and project closure. the Project planning is a crucial phase in the life cycle of the software project because it includes many challenging activities that are necessary; such as software estimation process that includes estimating the size of the software product to be produced, estimating the effort required, developing preliminary project schedules, and finally, estimating the overall cost of the project.^[1]

Agile Software Development (ASD) is a group of software development processes that are iterative, incremental, self-organizing, and emergent that continuously refined and prioritized following principles of Just In Time (JIT) management.^[2]

The main issue of determining effort estimation in the agile methodology is to focus on the effort and degree of difficulties of teamwork instead of an individual. Agile Software Development uses different techniques to deliver software products with maximum

customer satisfaction. Some of the techniques include XP (Extreme Programming) as shown in fig 1, Scrum Methodology, Adaptive Software Development (ASD). Some of the existing work shows that during the use of Agile Software Development, the team uses a story point approach to calculate the effort with the help of user story and project velocity as inputs. The main task is to estimate the required effort keeping in mind the technical complexity of the project.^[3]

Fig 1: Agile Extreme Programming (XP) Lifecycle

The calculation and understanding of estimation models based on user stories are difficult due to inherent complex relationships between the related friction factors. an implementation Level factor and relationships used to estimate software development effort could change over time and may differ for different software development environments. to address and overcome these problems, a new model with accurate estimation will be desired. The paper provides the solution that uses prediction model of a genetic algorithm as an optimization algorithm that can be used to improve the effort estimation accuracy in agile software development methodology by chromosomes that is made up of a gene pool that include user stories, friction factors, implementation Level factor, and dynamic forces.^[4]

2. Genetic Algorithm

In artificial intelligence (AI), an evolutionary algorithm (EA) is a subset of evolutionary computation, a generic population-based metaheuristic optimization algorithm. An evolutionary algorithm uses mechanisms inspired by biological evolution, such as reproduction, mutation, recombination, and selection. Candidate solutions to the optimization problem play the role of individuals in a population, and the fitness function determines the quality of the solutions. The evolution of the population then takes place after the repeated application of the above operators.^[5]

2.1 Genetic Algorithm Process

In Genetic evolutionary optimization Algorithms techniques that have several alternative solutions to transfer the problem from its real domain to the domain of evolutionary algorithms. the result of the solution is closer to the optimal, where the evolutionary process starts with the number of random solutions (population).^[6] These solutions (individuals) are then encoded according to the current problem, and the quality of each individual is evaluated through computation a fitness of each individual in the initial population, after which the current population changes to a new population as showing fig 2 by applying three basic operators:

Fig 2: Genetic Algorithm Flowchart

- 1) individuals Selection for reproduction using some of the selection mechanisms
- 2) Create an offspring using crossover and mutation operators. The probability of crossover and mutation are selected based on the application.
- 3) Compute the new generation of the population.

This process will end either when the maximum number of generations is reached or the optimal solution is found.

2.2 Algorithm

```
Choose an initial population of chromosomes;
while termination condition not satisfied do
  repeat
    if crossover condition satisfied then
      {select parent chromosomes;
       choose crossover parameters;
       perform crossover};
    if mutation condition satisfied then
      {choose mutation points;
       perform mutation};
    evaluate fitness of offspring
  until sufficient offspring created;
select new population;
endwhile
```

1) Start: Create a random population of potential solutions consisting of n individuals.

2) Fitness: Evaluate the fitness value $f(x)$ of each individual, x , in the population.

3) New population: Repeat the following steps to create a new population until completion of the new population.

4) Selection (Reproduction): The process of choosing the "best" parents in the community for mating, "best" is defined based on the current problem, has an active role in solving premature convergence resulting from a lack of diversity in the population, therefore identifying the appropriate selection technique is a critical step.^[7]

2.3 Genetic Algorithm Parameters

The parameters of the Genetic Algorithm, including the following:

1) **The size of the Population:** the selection of the size of the population is a critical issue, if the size of the population is very small, which means little search space, so it is possible to reach the local optimum. if the size of the population is too large, this will increase the area of search and increase the mathematical load, and therefore the process becomes slow, therefore, the size of the population must be reasonable.

2) **The rate of Crossover:** This determines the number of times a crossover occurs in the chromosomes in one generation, which is between 0%-100%; crossover rate is a delicate matter.

3) **The rate of Mutation:** Determines how many genes mutate in one generation; that between 0%-100%, and is also a delicate matter. decreases or Increases in the rate of mutation and crossover can have both a negative and positive effect.^[8]

4) **The number of generations:** Several cycles before termination. In some cases, hundreds of loops are sufficient and others are not, and this depends on the complexity of the problem.

All these Genetic Algorithm parameters are important because they determine the quality of the solution.

2.4 Biological Chromosomes in GA Algorithm

Can be surmised in the following points:

- 1) Genetic information is stored in the chromosomes
- 2) Each chromosome is built of DNA
- 3) Genes are encoded in the chromosomes
- 4) Genes code for proteins
- 5) Every gene has a unique position on the chromosome

The Chromosome in a genetic algorithm represents the set of possible combinations within the search space. It is commonly represented as a binary string of 0s and 1s as showing in Fig 3. In this paper, the Chromosome consists of the following parts: Story Point (SP), Implementation Level Factors (ILF), Friction Factors (FR), and Dynamic Forces. effectively constructing a population of SP, ILF, FR, DF. For SP considered two possibilities, represented by a binary string of 1 bit ($2^1 = 2$). For ILF, we considered three possible techniques, also represented by a binary string of 3 bits ($2^3 = 8$). For FR, DF, we considered twelve different possibilities, which required 4 bits to represent ($2^4 = 16$). With this Chromosome representation, the goal of the genetic algorithm is to find the Chromosome that maximizes a fitness function. We only worked with combinations within the proposed range. For example, the range of the attribute selection is between 1 to 5. This means that combinations with the attribute selection set of 6 to 8 are not valid.

Chromosome A	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
Chromosome B	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1

Fig 3: Binary String Example

3. Effort Estimation Techniques

To determine the process of the best-predicted effort required to develop a software project is termed as software effort estimation. This estimation can be divided into three levels. The first level consists of size estimation, the second level to involves effort estimation and the third level is the cost estimation, and the effort estimation is calculated in terms of (Person-Months).^[9]

Software effort estimation techniques can be classified into algorithmic and non-algorithmic models. The recent researches focused on an algorithmic model such as:

- 1) Line of Code (LOC).
- 2) Functions point matrices.

- 3) COCOMO and COCOMO-II.
- 4) Object points.
- 5) Software life cycle management.
- 6) Use case estimation.
- 7) Story points.

Agile software development methodology plays an important role in implementing communication goals between customers in a planned manner. The main issue of determining effort estimation in agile methods is to focus on the effort and degree of difficulties of teamwork rather than an individual. The main task is to estimate the required effort keeping in mind the technical complexity of the project. Agile software has many advantages as it is iterative, modular, incremental, customer-oriented and time-bound.^[10]

This paper focused on the factors of the story point to estimate the efforts in agile software development. The story point is the most common estimation technique for agile software development.

Story points refer to an estimate of the relative scale of the work in terms of actual development effort. Story Point estimation is done using relative sizing by comparing one story with a sample set of big sized stories.^[11] As Show in Teable1 Relative sizing across stories tends to be much more accurate over a larger sample, than trying to estimate each story for the effort involved. Planning poker is one of the most useful tools in agile software development.

Table 1: Story Point (SP) wights

Terms	S	Wight
Very Small Story	VSS	1
Small Story	SS	2
Medium Story	MS	3
Large Story	LS	5
Very Large Story	VLS	8

Table 1 shows the weight of Story Point (SP) which can have many iterations depending upon the system requirements. The weights assigned to each customer or user stories are predicted.

In Implementation Life Factors (ILF) includes the terms Off the Shelf (OS), Full Experience Components (FEC), Partial Experience Components (PEC), and New Components (NC). as shows in Table 2 the scaling factor for implementation level which represents the level of understanding each user story.

Table 2: Implemntation Life Factors (ILF) Scale

Term	Ser	Scale
Off the Shelf	OS	1
Full Experience Components	FEC	2
Partial Experience Components	PEC	3
New Components	NC	4

The optimization process refers to study the constraints of a project that should be completed before

the calibration to improve the stability of the velocity calculation. This process includes two factors are Friction Factor (FR) and Dynamic Forces (DF).

The friction includes a range of factors that may affect the team velocity they are team composition, the process, environmental factors, and dynamic of the team. as shown in Table 3. the composition of the team concerns the skills and attitudes of team members. The process factor refers to the percentage of change in the agile methods, release, building, and testing. The environmental factors refer to the noise, poor ventilation, poor lighting, uncomfortable seating and desks, inadequate hardware, or software. Team dynamics are patterns of interaction among team members that determine the performance of the team.

Table 3: Friction Factors (FR)

Friction factors	Stable	volatile	Highly volatile	Very highly volatile
Team composition	1	.98	.95	.91
Process	1	.98	.94	.89
Environmental factors	1	.99	.98	.96
Team dynamic	1	.98	.91	.85

As shown in Table 3 the Friction Factors (FR) with a range of values. Each factor has been adjusted according to their risk level (stable, volatile, highly volatile, and very highly volatile).

The dynamic forces (DF) refers to the factors that could lead to a loss of velocity. These factors are unexpected or non-predictable. The dynamic forces (DF) include some of the factors - team changes, new tools, vendor defects, responsibilities out of the project, personal issues, stakeholders, unclear requirements, changing requirements, and reallocation. as shown in Table 4, Those factors are ranked from (Normal, high, very high, and extra high).^[12]

Table 4: Dynamic Forces (DF) variables

Variable Factors	Normal	High	Very High	Extra-High
Expected to team change	1	.98	.95	.91
Introduction to a new tool	1	.99	.97	.96
Vendor's Defect	1	.98	.94	.90
Responsibilities out of the project	1	.99	.98	.98
Personal Issues	1	.99	.99	.98
Expected Delay in Stakeholder response	1	.99	.98	.96
Expected Ambiguity in Details	1	.98	.97	.95
Expected Changes in environment	1	.99	.98	.97
Expected Relocation	1	.99	.99	.98

when the project is complete, the effort will be the sum of membership degree of Story Point (SP), Implementation Life Factors (ILF), and population of all individual user stories. The Eq. (2) shows the fuzzy

story size (FSS) by using the triangle membership function μ .

3.1 Performance Criteria

There are some of the performance measures criteria existing in the some of literature. The performance of different models can be evaluated by using the main criteria as the following:

1) Mean size of relative error- It is used to calculate the percentage of the difference between the actual and estimated effort and finally assess the relative error averaged over a large number of values for a set of the effort.^[13]

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|Actual_i - Predicted_i|}{Actual_i}$$

actual i , is the actual effort required of i the data test, predicted i , is the estimated effort from the prediction of i data test. N represents the total count of variables in the dataset.^[14]

2) Mean squared error is used to calculate the square of mean relative error by finding the difference between estimated effort, actual and dividing by the total number of datasets^[15]

$$\frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (Actual_i - Predicted_i)^2}{N}$$

3) The third performance measure metric is the percentage of prediction that represented as PRED(x), given by

$$Pred(x) = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Q_i$$

$$Q_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (MMRE_i) < \frac{x}{100} \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $x = 25$.

4) when complete the project, the effort will be the sum of membership degree of SP, ILF, and Com for all individual user stories. The below Equation shows the fuzzy story size (FSS) by using the triangle membership function μ .^[16]

$$FSS = SP \cdot \mu_{SP} \times \sum_i^4 ILF \cdot \mu_i^{ILF} \times \sum_i^5 Com \cdot \mu_i^{Com}$$

5) Fuzzy FR (FFR) is calculated as the product of all four components of FR and the membership degree. The below equation Shows the FFR calculation by using the triangle membership function μ :^[17]

$$FFR = \prod_{i=1}^4 FR \cdot \mu_i^{FF}$$

4. Proposed Algorithm

The proposed design is calculating the effort estimation in agile software development by creating a Multi-Population of Genetic Algorithm as showing in Fig 4. the effort estimation is calculated as offspring generated by inbreeding and crossbreeding in each phase from software project implementation phases, and the candidate for each population of the next generation, each population include two chromosomes. [18] [19] The Proposed algorithm is described as follows:

1) **Start-** Initializing Population, by creating a two population of potential solutions consisting of n individuals.

Population (A) - include two chromosomes, the first one called (Story Point) SP Chromosome as shown in Table 5, which contains some of the gens. each gene is representing a weight of Story Point factors, and the second chromosome called Implementation Life Factors (ILF), which also contains some of the gens. each gene is representing a scale of ILF scales.

Population (B) - include two chromosomes, the first one called Friction Factor (FR) Chromosome, That Contains some of the gens. each gene is representing a risk factor of FR scales. and the second chromosome called Dynamic Forces (DF), which also contains some of the gens. each gene is representing a variable of DF factors. [20]

Fig 3: Multi Population of Genetic Algorithm

2) **Fitness** - Evaluate the fitness value $f(x)$ of each individual, x , in the population (A), then Evaluate the fitness value in the population (B)

Story Point (SP) Chromosome:

Table 5 shows SP Chromosome which can have many iterations depending upon the system requirements. The weights assigned for each user stories are predicted.

Table 5: Story Point (SP) Chromosome

0001	0010	0011	0101	1000
1	2	3	5	8
VSS	SS	MS	LS	VLS
Very Small Story	Small Story	Medium Story	Large Story	Very Large Story

Implementation life factors (ILF) Chromosome

Table 6 shows (ILF) Chromosome scaling factor for implementation level which represents the level of understanding each user story, that include terms Off the Shelf (OS), Full Experience Components (FEC), Partial Experience Components (PEC), and New Components (NC).

Table 6: (ILF) Chromosome

0001	0010	0011	0100
1	2	3	4
OS	FEC	PEC	NC
Off the Shelf	Full Experience Components	Partial Experience Components	New Components

Friction Factors (FR) Chromosome

Table 7 shows the (FR) Chromosome, with a range of values. Each factor has been adjusted according to their risk level (stable, volatile, highly volatile, and very highly volatile).

Table 7: Friction Factor (FR) Chromosome

	Stable	Volatile	Highly volatile	Very highly volatile
	4	3	2	1
Team composition	0100	0011	0010	0001
Process	0100	0011	0010	0001
Environmental factors	0100	0011	0010	0001
Team dynamic	0100	0011	0010	0001
Team composition	0100	0011	0010	0001

Friction Factors (FR) Chromosome

Table 8 shows the (DF) Chromosomes refers to the factors that could lead to loss of velocity. These factors are unpredictable and unexpected.

Table 8: Dynamic Forces (DF) Chromosome

	Normal	High	Very High	Extra-High
Expected to team change	0001	0010	0011	0100
Introduction to a new tool	0001	0010	0011	0100
Vendor's Defect	0001	0010	0011	0100
Responsibilities out of the project	0001	0010	0011	0100
Personal Issues	0001	0010	0011	0100
Expected Ambiguity in Details	0001	0010	0011	0100
Expected Changes in the environment	0001	0010	0011	0100
Expected Relocation	0001	0010	0011	0100

After the change, all estimation effort techniques (SP, ILF, FR, DF) to genes in chromosomes will perform some operations of genetic algorithm (Selection, Crossover, Mutation) Severally for each population.

Assuming we have an agile software, project divided into sub-projects and we put random values of a story point in the population (A) shows Table 9- as the following:

Table 9: Population A

	SP ₁	SP ₂	SP ₃	SP ₄	SP ₅	SP ₆
Project 1	2.4	0.7	8	-2	5	1.1
Project 2	-0.4	2.7	5	-0.1	7	0.1
Project 2	-0.1	2	2	-3	2	0.9
Project 3	4	7	12	6.1	1.4	-4
Project 4	3.1	4	0	2.4	4.8	0
Project 5	-2	3	-7	6	3	3

As showing in Table 10 – the 6 stories point (SP) with total estimation effort (44.1%) in the first project. that can enhance the result for estimation effort and each story point (SP) will represent a gen in the genetic algorithm chromosome.

Table 10: project 1 Chromosome

Gen ₀	Gen ₁	Gen ₂	Gen ₃	Gen ₄	Gen ₅	Chromosome 1
SP ₁	SP ₂	SP ₃	SP ₄	SP ₅	SP ₆	SP Project 1
2.4	0.7	8	-2	5	1.1	44.1
SS	SS	VLS	SS	VLS	SS	

The $SP = SP_1 Gen_0 + SP_2 Gen_1 + SP_3 Gen_2 + SP_4 Gen_3 + SP_5 Gen_4 + SP_6 Gen_5$

The goal is to find the set of parameters (SP1:SP6) that map the following input to its output $SP' = 4 SP_1 + 2 SP_2 + 7 SP_3 + 5 SP_4 + 11 SP_5 + SP_6$ To calculate the fitness function using the following equation in the regression model:

$$F(c) = \frac{1}{error} = \frac{1}{|SP - SP'|}$$

$$SP' = 4 SP_1 + 2 SP_2 + 7 SP_3 + 5 SP_4 + 11 SP_5 + SP_6$$

$$SP' = 4 \times 2.4 - 2 \times 0.7 + 7 \times 8 + 5 \times -2 + 11 \times 5 + 1.1$$

$$SP' = 110.3$$

$$F(c) = \frac{1}{error} = \frac{1}{|44.1 - 110.3|} = \frac{1}{66.2} = 0.015$$

Then calculate the fitness function for all chromosomes in the population (A) with the same previous steps as shown in Table 11.

Table 11: Fitness Function for all Chromosomes

Story Points (SP Chromosomes) – Population A						SP'	F(C)
2.4	0.7	8	-2	5	1.1	110.3	0.015
-0.4	2.7	5	-0.1	7	0.1	100.1	0.018
-0.1	2	2	-3	2	0.9	13.9	0.033
4	7	12	6.1	1.4	-4	127.9	0.012
3.1	4	0	2.4	4.8	0	69.2	0.04
-2	3	-7	6	3	3	3	0.024

3) **Selection** – The individuals in this type are selected according to their rank, but first we need to sort the chromosomes based on their fitness value. this process will be choosing the best parents or the best chromosomes from table 12 Which carries the best fitness function.

As shown in Table 12 the best parents from population A

Table 12: Best Chromosomes

Story Points (SP Chromosomes) – Population A						SP'	F(C)	
P1	-0.1	2	2	-3	2	0.9	13.9	0.033
P2	3.1	4	0	2.4	4.8	0	69.2	0.04
P3	-2	3	-7	6	3	3	3	0.024

4) **Crossover** - in this operation will take two parents (chromosomes) to generate a new offspring by switching segments of the parent genes. It is more likely that the new offspring (children) as shown in fig 4 will contain a good part of their parents, and consequently perform better as compared to their ancestors.

Fig 4: Crossover operation

The first crossover between two parents (P₁, P₂) as showing in fig 5 to generate new offspring.

Fig 5: New Generate of Offspring

Then makes a crossover between other parents (P₁, P₂) with the same previous steps.

5) **Mutation** – The mutation is one of the most important phases of the genetic algorithm, by using random of values of the story point factors (VSS, SS, MS, LS, VLS), where it is changed or is switched between specific genes within a single chromosome to create chromosomes, that provide new enhancement solutions for the generation of estimation effort.

Fig 6: New Generate of Offspring

As shown in Fig 6 the describe the mutation of the chromosome by replacing the gene (4.8) with the gene (2.4) as a random value from story point factors.

Then makes the mutation for all chromosomes that generated form the crossover phase, with the same previous steps.

After complete, the mutation phase will become the first generation of the Population (A) as show the generation 1 in Table 13.

Table 13: Generation 1 from Population A

Generation 0 – Population A						
P1	-0.1	2	2	-3	2	0.9
P2	3.1	4	0	2.4	4.8	0
P3	-2	3	-7	6	3	3
Generation 1 – Population A						
P1	-0.1	2	2	2.4	4.8	0
P2	3.1	4	0	6	3	3
P3	-2	3	-7	-3	2	0.9

When the new generation generated from the population (A), all the phases of the genetic algorithm will be re-applied on this generation (Fitness value, Selection, Crossover, Mutation). The algorithm will be stopped when achieves the goal, after completing the mating pool of all chromosomes and completing the mutation phase for all genes in the population, that use random values of the story points factors, To ensure that all point stories are addressed to extract effort estimation for only story points Technique. can change the value of the gene of story point (SP) chromosomes to binary sting if the gene contains a set of attributes.

In implementation Life Factors (ILF) technique, that the second chromosomes of the population (A) and the Population (B), that include two chromosomes (Friction Factor FR, Dynamic Forces DF), will be apply the proposed genetic algorithm phases (Fitness value, Selection, Crossover, Mutation), with the same previous steps in all phases. The purpose of using the Multi-Genetic Algorithm to accelerate the algorithm, by dividing each of the two chromosomes into one population.

5. Results

The Genetic Algorithm parameters that were selected in the first test of the population (A), Which underwent a set of proposed algorithm operations showed the following results for effort estimation for story points chromosomes:

Fig 7: Effort Estimation of SP

as shown in Fig 7 the proposed algorithm producing an accurate estimation of effort for story point.

In implementation Life Factors (ILF) Chromosomes, the proposed genetic algorithm extracted accurate results, which represents the level of understanding each user story.

Fig 8: Effort Estimation of ILF

Fig 9 shows the proposed genetic algorithm extract the effort estimation for dynamic forces assigned values, which refers to the factors that could lead to loss of velocity. The factors are ranked from (Normal, high, very high, and extra high)

Fig 9: Effort Estimation of Dynamic Forces

Fig 10 shows the Effort Estimation for friction factor FR with a range of values, also put each factor according to their risk level (stable, volatile, highly volatile, and very highly volatile).

Fig 10: Effort Estimation - Friction Factor

6. Conclusion

This paper aimed to propose to improve the effort estimation in agile software development methodology by using Multi - genetic algorithm. the proposed model has been put a population of candidate solutions for (Story Points, Implementation Life Factors, Fraction Factors, and Dynamic forces) to optimization the effort estimation in agile software development methodology. Each candidate solution has a set of properties (Parents, chromosomes) which can be mutated and altered; traditionally, solutions fit represented in decimal or binary as strings of 0s and 1s, and other encodings are also possible.

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